

TITLE: ROLE OF THE CONCEPT OF COLLECTIVE SECURITY IN THE 21ST CENTURY.

SHORT TITLE: COLLECTIVE SECURITY IN THE 21ST CENTURY.

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ROLE OF THE CONCEPT OF COLLECTIVE SECURITY IN THE 21ST CENTURY.

Abstract

With tensions in Syria and the Korean peninsula at their highest in two decades, it becomes imperative to analyse the concept of collective security. With the exception of economic sanctions authorized under Article 41, the system of collective security as envisioned in Chapter VII of the UN Charter is dormant. This article seeks to analyse the establishment of collective security in the Charter within the functional and judicial parameters of the UN; an evolution that legitimized the use of force for the preservation of international peace and security. The article begins by briefly defining the powers of the Security Council to authorize collective security and how the Security Council is bound by human rights in its sanctions practice. It then critically analyses the role of collective security in ensuring peace and security in the world. The article proffers that to a large extent, the concept of collective security has failed.

Key words: International Law- Security Council- Collective Security- Economic Sanctions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Collective Security can be understood as a security arrangement where a group of countries pledge co-operative joint action in the eyes of threat to their economic or territorial sovereignty. With shrinking global boundaries and the concept of a global village, the states have become subjects of one global body. This global body is to act

as a superior force to govern relations between the individual units. It is this idea that led to the formation of international bodies such as the League of Nations and the United Nations (UN) were formed. Inter alia other concepts, Collective Security has formed the foundation of international bodies of these bodies.

A collective security system guarantees the security of each member state against any war or aggression, which may be committed, by any state against any other state. It is like an insurance system in which all the nations are bound to protect the victim of an aggression or war by neutralizing the aggression or war against the victim. Collective Security stands for a universal system in which all states of the world, without any discrimination, undertake to meet any aggression anywhere in the system, and against any aggressor. The underlying principle of collective security has been 'One for All and All for One'. Aggression or war against any one nation is a war against all the nations. Therefore all the nations are to act collectively against every War/Aggression. As such, Collective Security constitutes a modern device of crisis management. All the members of community of nations are expected to act and save the humankind from the scourge of war and aggression and to use the collective security system for this purpose. Collective Security is different from a collective defence system, which is an alliance involving a regional defence system. A collective defence arrangement is made by a group of nations who have a common perception of threat to their security from a common enemy.

The UN Charter (Charter)¹ is a meticulously drafted short treaty of less than 9,000 words and is the foundational treaty of the United Nations organization. The Charter includes a system of collective security that is designed to meet an international crisis resulting from war or aggression or a threat of war or aggression in any part of the international system. The UN collective security system is based on the complementary nature of two fundamental structural criteria. First, "In order to ensure prompt and effective action by the United Nations, its Members confer on the Security Council primary responsibility for the maintenance of international peace and security ..."². Second, "All Members of the United Nations, in order to contribute

¹ Adopted 26 June 1945 and entered into force 24 October 1945. United Nations, *Charter of the United Nations*, 24 October 1945, 1 UNTS XVI.

Available at: <http://www.un.org/aboutun/charter/index.html>. In addition, the Charter of the United Nations is always reprinted in the most current Volume of the Yearbook of the United Nations.

² *Ibid.* See Article 24.

to the maintenance of international peace and security, undertake to make available to the Security Council, on its call and in accordance with a special agreement or agreements, armed forces, assistance, and facilities, including rights of passage, necessary for the purpose of maintaining international peace and security”³. After sixty- five years neither of these fundamental ideas has been implemented in full.

II. THE UNITED NATIONS COLLECTIVE SECURITY SYSTEM AND THE SECURITY COUNCIL.

The Charter regards the preservation of international peace and security as its most major objective. In the Charter, the phrase “International Peace and Security” has been used 32 times. In its very first article, while stating the purposes of the United Nations, it makes the preservation of international peace and security as the first priority. It lays down a collective security system for this purpose.

Article 2 (4) of the Charter states that “All Members shall refrain in their international relations from the threat or use of force against the territorial integrity or political independence of any state, or in any other manner inconsistent with the Purposes of the United Nations”⁴. Thus, the Security Council has the primary responsibility for the maintenance of international peace and security. Furthermore, Article 2 (7) of the Charter adds that, “this principle shall not prejudice the application of enforcement measures under Chapter VII”⁵.

To this end, a Collective Security system has been laid down in Chapter VII of the Charter and its title reads: “Action with respect to Threats to the Peace, Breaches of the Peace, and Acts of Aggression”⁶. It contains 13 Articles, from Article 39 to 51 that together provide for a collective system for preserving international peace and security. Article 39 makes it the responsibility of the Security Council to determine the existence of any threat to the peace, breach of peace, or act of aggression and to decide about measures that are to be taken for managing crisis for restoring

³ *Ibid.* See Article 43.

⁴ *Ibid.* See Article 2(4).

⁵ *Ibid.* See Article 2(7).

⁶ *Ibid.* See Articles 39-51.

international peace and security. Article 40 lays down that as the first step towards preventing the aggravation of the situation involving a threat to or breach of international peace and security, the Security Council can take provisional measures like cease fire, and call upon the concerned parties to comply with these. Article 41 refers to the enforcement actions, other than the collective military action that the Security Council can recommend to the members of the United Nations for compelling the concerned parties to end the violation of peace and security. It can recommend sanctions against the state involved in aggression. Article 42 empowers the Security Council to take military action for securing or maintaining international peace and security. Art. 43 makes it the responsibility of all the members of the United Nations to contribute their support, efforts, resources and forces for raising the Collective Security force that may have to be raised when the Security Council decides to undertake action under Article 42.

The next four Articles of the Charter⁷ lay down the procedure for raising, maintaining and using the UN PeaceKeeping Force for Collective Security force. Article 48 states that the action required to carry out the decision of the Security Council for the maintenance of international peace and security shall be taken by all the members of the United Nations, or by some of them, as the Security Council may determine. Whilst Article 49 asserts that the members of the United Nations shall join in affording mutual assistance in-carrying out measures decided upon by the Security Council. Article 50 further lays down the ways in which non-member states can adjust their policies and actions towards the decision that may be taken up by the Security Council under Articles 41 and 42. However, Article 51 accepts the right of the states to individual or collective self-defence if an armed attack occurs against a member, until the Security Council has taken the measures necessary to maintain international peace and security. With all these provisions, Chapter VII of the Charter lays down the Collective Security system for preservation of international peace and security.

The Security Council has been assigned the responsibility and power to initiate collective security action for meeting any threat to international peace by a war or aggression. It is a political body; entitled to adopt measures having legal

⁷ *Ibid.* See Article 44-47.

consequences. The competence granted to the Security Council by the Charter is a normative one. Under Chapter VII it can take enforcement action to maintain or restore international peace and security. Such measures range from economic sanctions to military interventions in case the Security Council has previously established the existence of “any threat to the peace, breach of the peace or act of aggression”⁸. After a decision under Article 39 stating that a situation constitutes any threat to, or breach of the peace, the Security Council can order states to undertake provisional measures under Article 40, or take enforcement actions normally referred to as sanctions under Article 41 and finally, it can take military action under Article 42, against the entity responsible for the threat or breach⁹. The Security Council seldom states explicitly on which article it is basing its resolution, it usually only states that it is “acting under Chapter VII of the Charter¹⁰.” The only recourse the Security Council has for the enforcement of peace and security is military action led by coalitions of member states that are not under the United Nations purview. The UN has also evolved a customary practice under Chapter VII of the Charter whereby the Security Council may authorise States to use armed force in order to give effect to its decisions under Article 39 for example, the eviction of Iraq from Kuwait by a Security Council authorised multinational force in 1991. Thus, the general concept of international peace and security can cover all kinds of situations¹¹.

A question arises in this respect as to whether the choice of the Security Council is limited to the measures provided for in Articles 41 and 42 of the Charter (as the wording of Article 39 suggests), or whether it has even broader discretion in the form of general powers to maintain and restore international peace and security under Chapter VII. In the latter case one does not have to find every measure decided by the Security Council under Chapter VII within the confines of Articles 41 and 42, or possibly Article 40. Whatever the case, under both interpretations, the Security

⁸ *Ibid.* See Article 39.

⁹ I. Österdahl, *Threat to the Peace*, 1998; J.A. Frowein, “Article 41 and Article 42”, in: B. Simma (ed.), *The Charter of the United Nations: A Commentary*, 1995, 621 et seq.

¹⁰ S/RES/824 (1993) of 6 May 1993; S/RES/841 (1993) of 16 June 1993; S/RES/917 (1994) of 6 May 1994; S/RES/1160 (1998) of 31 March 1998.

¹¹ ICTY Appeals Chamber *Tadić* Decision 1995 IT-94-1-AR72, para. 28.

Council has broad discretion in deciding on the course of action and evaluating the appropriateness of the measures to be taken. The wording of Article 39 is quite clear as to the channelling of the very broad and exceptional powers of the Security Council under Chapter VII through Articles 41 and 42. These two articles leave the Security Council a wide choice. This consideration is reinforced by the fact that the Security Council is not a law enforcement organ, but it enjoys unfettered discretions as a political one. Indeed, the Charter recognises the Security Council's powers and tasks as those of a political organ enjoying a wide margin of discretion regarding how to maintain or restore international peace and security. This idea was stressed by Kelsen, who stated that, "the purpose of the enforcement action under Article 39 is not to maintain or restore the law, but to maintain, or restore peace, which is not necessarily identical with the law"¹²."

The broad scope of action has enabled the Security Council to act against non-state actors such as mercenaries¹³, rebel groups¹⁴ and against specific individuals that can be individually identified¹⁵. Some writers consider an alternative view of UN sanctions under Article 41, at least potentially, as a kind of economic warfare, i.e. non-forcible measures regularly undertaken in wartime alongside (or instead of) armed measures, for the purpose of harming or defeating the enemy, rather than as peacetime countermeasures¹⁶. Subsequently, the list of Article 41 is non-exhaustive¹⁷. The most frequently adopted sanctions have covered selective embargoes¹⁸,

¹² H. Kelsen, *The Law of the United Nations*, 1951, 294.

¹³ S/RES/1457 (2003) of 24 January 2003; S/RES/1474 (2003) of 8 April 2003.

¹⁴ S/RES/1521 (2003) of 22 December 2003.

¹⁵ In the case of Liberia; S/RES/1343 (2001) of 7 March 2001; S/RES/1521 (2003) of 22 December 2003; S/RES/1638 (2005) of 11 November 2005; S/RES/1523 (2004) of 30 January 2004, concerning Western Sahara. In case of Afghanistan and Al-Qaida, S/RES/1390 (2002) of 16 January 2002; S/RES/1455 (2003) of 17 January 2003; S/RES/1526 (2004) of 30 January 2004; S/RES/1617 (2005) of 29 July 2005; S/RES/1735 (2006) of 22 December 2006; S/RES/1822 (2008) of 30 June 2008.

¹⁶ F. Stenhammar, "United Nations Targeted Sanctions, the International Rule of Law and the European Court of Justice's Judgment in Kadi and al-Barakat", *Nord. J. Int'l L.* 79 (2010), 113 et seq. (120)

¹⁷ N.J. Schrijver, "The Use of Economic Sanctions by the UN Security Council: An International Law Perspective", in: H.H.G. Post (ed.), *International Economic Law and Armed Conflict*, 1994, 128

prohibitions of export and import¹⁹, prohibitions of service²⁰, prohibitions of movement of funds and freezing of funds and assets²¹, prohibition of air, sea and land communications²², severance or reductions of diplomatic and other relations²³ and restrictions of movement of persons²⁴ as a means to enforce the effectiveness of its other measures²⁵.

¹⁸ Oil in the case of Haiti with Resolution S/RES/917 (1994) of 6 May 1994, the Security Council expanded the embargo to include all commodities and products, with the exception of medical supplies and foodstuffs. The expanded embargo went into effect on 21 May 1994. S/RES/661 (1990) of 6 August 1990, against Iraq; arms and related material in the case of the Former Yugoslavia S/RES/713 (1991) of 25 September 1991. In Resolution S/RES/788 (1992) of 19 November 1992, the Security Council imposed an arms embargo on Liberia; S/RES/918 (1994) of 17 May 1994 concerning Rwanda; S/RES/1493 (2003) of 28 July 2003, concerning the Democratic Republic of the Congo.

¹⁹ S/RES/661 (1990) of 6 August 1990, concerning Iraq-Kuwait; S/RES/757 (1992) of 30 May 1992, concerning the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia; S/RES/917 (1994) of 6 May 1994, concerning Haiti. Regarding the specific prohibition of export and import of diamonds, see S/RES/1295 (2000) of 18 April 2000 on the situation in Angola; S/RES/1306 (2000) of 5 July 2000, S/RES/1385 (2001) of 19 December 2001, both on the situation in Sierra Leone; S/RES/1343 (2001) of 7 March 2001, on the situation in Liberia.

²⁰ S/RES/1127 (1997) of 28 August 1997, concerning Angola.

²¹ In Resolution S/RES/883 (1993) of 11 November 1993, the Security Council tightened sanctions, approving the freezing of Libyan funds and financial resources in other countries and the prohibition on providing equipment to Libya for oil refinery and transport. With regard to Bosnia and Herzegovina, see S/RES/820 (1993) of 17 April 1993; Libya S/RES/883 (1993) of 11 November 1993; Bosnian Serbs S/RES/942 (1994) of 23 September 1994; against Osama bin Laden, the Taliban and other entities, S/RES/1267 (1999) of 15 October 1999; S/RES/1333 (2000) of 19 December 2000; S/RES/1390 (2002) of 16 January 2002.

²² S/RES/665 (1990) of 25 August 1990 on the situation in Iraq; S/RES/1221 (1999) of 12 January 1999 about the UNITA; S/RES/820 (1993) of 17 April 1993 on the situation in Bosnia and Herzegovina and S/RES/1267 (1999) of 15 October 1999 on Afghanistan.

²³ Question concerning the situation in Southern Rhodesia, S/RES/217 (1965) of 20 November 1965; S/RES/253 (1968) of 29 May 1968; S/RES/277 (1970) of 15 March 1970; Libya, S/RES/748 (1992) of 31 March 1992; Bosnia and Herzegovina, S/RES/757 (1992) of 30 May 1992; Angola, S/RES/1173 (1998) of 12 June 1998 and against the Taliban, S/RES/1333 (2000) of 19 December 2000.

²⁴ S/RES/1054 (1996) of 26 April 1996 in case of Sudan; S/RES/1137 (1997) of 12 November 1997, on the situation between Iraq and Kuwait; S/RES/1343 (2001) of 7 March 2001, concerning Liberia; S/RES/942 (1994) of 23 September 1994, concerning Bosnia and Herzegovina; S/RES/1171 (1998) of 5 June 1998 in case of Sierra Leone; S/RES/1333 (2000) of 19 December 2000 against the Taliban.

²⁵ In Resolution S/RES/1132 (1997) of 8 October 1997, the Security Council imposed an oil and arms embargo on Sierra Leone, as well as travel restrictions for members of the military junta of Sierra Leone. The Security Council imposed several embargoes on the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia: firstly, in Resolution S/RES/713 (1991) of 25 September 1991, the Security Council imposed a general and complete embargo on all deliveries of weapons and military equipment. One year later, in its Resolution S/RES/757 (1992) of 30 May 1992, the Security Council imposed economic and other sanctions on the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia, including a full trade embargo, a flight ban and the prevention of the participation of the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia in sporting and cultural events.

The sanctions resolutions also usually contained humanitarian and other exceptions²⁶, medical equipment and foodstuffs in humanitarian circumstances being generally excepted, although the resolutions have shown great inconsistency in other types of exceptions²⁷.

The Security Council has also enabled the system of collective security to stop child abuse²⁸, to ensure the safety of its staff²⁹, against the recruitment of child soldiers³⁰, against failure to protect civilians during armed conflict³¹ and control the risks of small arms trafficking³². From the foregoing, it is clear that the Security Council understands its delegated power in a dynamic way³³, and therefore has not hesitated to authorise many different measures under Chapter VII.

Finally, in Resolution S/RES/942 (1994) of 23 September 1994, the Security Council imposed comprehensive economic and diplomatic sanctions on Bosnian Serb military forces.

²⁶ For instance, in Resolution S/RES/1070 (1996) of 16 August 1996, the Security Council decided to impose an air embargo on Sudan; however, the sanctions measures adopted, which were to enter into force pending a decision by the Council within 90 days after the date of the adoption of Resolution S/RES/1070 (1996), was not imposed, for humanitarian reasons.

²⁷ S/RES/841 (1993) of 16 June 1993, on the situation in Haiti; S/RES/1284 (1999) of 17 December 1999 on the situation between Iraq and Kuwait; S/RES/1110 (1997) of 28 May 1997, on the situation in the former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia; S/RES/1133 (1997) of 20 October 1997, on the situation concerning Western Sahara; S/RES/1132 (1997) of 8 October 1997, on the situation in Sierra Leone; S/RES/1343 (2001) of 7 March 2001, on the situation in Liberia; S/RES/1005 (1995) of 17 July 1995, on the supply of an appropriate quantity of explosives for the use in the demining operations in Rwanda; S/RES/1333 (2000) of 19 December 2000 on the situation in Afghanistan; S/RES/1298 (2000) of 17 May 2000 on the situation in Eritrea/Ethiopia; S/RES/1390 (2002) of 16 January 2002 against the Taliban and Al-Qaida.

²⁸ S/RES/1325 (2000) of 31 October 2000; S/RES/1445 (2002) of 4 December 2002.

²⁹ S/RES/1296 (2000) of 19 April 2000, op. para. 5.

³⁰ S/RES/1612 (2005) of 26 July 2005; S/RES/1460 (2003) of 30 January 2003; S/RES/1379 (2001) of 20 November 2001; S/RES/1314 (2000) of 11 August 2000.

³¹ S/RES/1738 (2006) of 23 December 2006; S/RES/1674 (2006) of 28 April 2006

³² S/RES/1467 (2003) of 18 March 2003.

³³ Ch. Tomuschat, "International Law as the Constitution of Mankind", in: International Law Commission (ed.), *International Law on the Eve of the Twenty-first Century: Views from the International Law Commission*, 1997, 37 et seq.; D. Sarooshi, *The United Nations and the Development of Collective Security: The Delegation by the UN Security Council of its Chapter VII powers*, 1999, 174; T.D. Gill, "Legal and some political limitations on the power of the UN Security Council to exercise its enforcement powers under Chapter VII of the Charter", *NYIL* 26 (1995), 33 et seq. (70- 71).

As already said, the Security Council's powers under Chapter VII are quite broad, but nevertheless are also subject to limitations³⁴. There are two types of possible limits to the Security Council's action, one being substantive, and the other formal. Herdegen has recently suggested a number of substantive limits to the actions of the Security Council³⁵. Gowlland-Debbas has also drawn up a list of rules and principles, which the Security Council may not violate³⁶. Nolte has doubts about this theoretical substantive approach insisting that the point at which an excessive use by the Security Council of its powers becomes manifest must be determined by reference to all the factors of the specific case³⁷. Some other commentators have argued that the Security Council can act above international law and therefore no legal substantial limits exist on measures adopted by it under Chapter VII³⁸. This interpretation is based on the wording of Articles 25 and 103 of the Charter. According to Article 25 of the Charter, the UN Members "agree to accept and carry out the decisions of the Security Council in accordance with the present Charter." Specifically, Article 103 states, "in the event of a conflict between the obligations of the Members of the United Nations under the present Charter and their obligations under any other international agreement, their obligations under the present Charter shall prevail." Therefore, it has been argued that Article 103 of the Charter allows states to disregard e.g. human rights treaty

³⁴ I. Brownlie, "International Law at the Fiftieth Anniversary of the United Nations", *RdC* 255 (1995), 217 et seq., who considers that "the Council thus acts as agent of all the members and not independently of their wishes; it is moreover, bound by the Purposes and Principles of the Organization, so that it cannot, in principle, act arbitrarily and unfettered by any re-straints." In other words, but a similar idea, see, J. Delbrück, "Article 24", in: B. Simma (ed.), *The Charter of the United Nations. A Commentary*, 2002, 403, 406; R. Higgins, "The Advisory Opinion on Namibia. Which UN Resolutions are Binding under Article 25 of the Charter?", *ICLQ* 21 (1972), 278 et seq.; K. Zemanek, "Is the Security Council the sole judge of its own legality?", in: E. Yakpo/ T. Boumedra (eds), *Liber Amicorum Mohamed Bedjaoui*, 1999, 640 et seq.

³⁵ M. Herdegen, *Befugnisse des UN-Sicherheitsrates – Aufgeklärter Absolutismus im Völkerrecht?*, 1998, 15.

³⁶ V. Gowlland-Debbas, "The Functions of the United Nations Security Council in the International Legal System", in: M. Bayers (ed.) *The role of law in international politics: essays in international relations and international law*, 2000, 277-300.

³⁷ G. Nolte, "The Limits of the Security Council's Powers and its Functions in the International Legal System: Some Reflections", in: M. Byers (ed.), *The Role of Law in International Politics*, 2000, 321.

³⁸ G. Oosthuizen, "Playing the Devil's Advocate: the United Nations Security Council is Unbound by Law", *LJIL* 12 (1999), 549

obligations in the execution of Security Council resolutions³⁹. There are, however, opposing views, for instance, those of Alvarez, according to whom Article 103 makes the Security Council decision prevail over both treaty and customary law⁴⁰. However, according to the clear wording of Article 103, the Charter shall only prevail in the event of a conflict between an obligation of a Member State under the present Charter and its obligation under any international agreement⁴¹, but not under general international law⁴². Whatever the merits of this argument, Article 103 could never override the operation of norms that have peremptory status. As Judge Lauterpacht's Separate Opinion points out, even if the Charter prevails over other international agreements, the "relief which Article 103 of the Charter may give the Security Council in case of conflict between one of its decision and an operative treaty obligation cannot – as a matter of simple hierarchy of norms – extend to a conflict between a Security Council Resolution and *jus cogens*⁴³. As the core human rights are part of *jus cogens*, Article 103 would not allow a Security Council decision to prevail over, for instance, the prohibition of genocide and torture or other inhumane treatment⁴⁴. Thus, the interpretation that Article 103 obligations prevail over both treaty and customary law cannot be accepted for the following reasons. First of all, according to Article 24 (1), read together with Articles 1 and 2 of the Charter, the Security Council's decisions must be in accord with the purposes and principles of the

³⁹ The prevalence of the UN Charter over the ICCPR with regard to article 1 was declared by the United Kingdom upon signature (<<http://www.unhchr.ch/html/menu3/b/>>). The United Kingdom in its derogation of 18 December 2001 did not explicitly refer to Article 103. Indeed it based its derogation on article 4 of the ICCPR. But it made reference to SC Resolution S/RES/1373 (2001) of 28 September 2001 requiring all states to take measures to prevent terrorist attacks.

⁴⁰ J. Alvarez, "The Security Council's war on terrorism: problems and policy option", in: E. de Wet/ A. Nollkaemper (eds), *Review of the Security Council by Members States*, 2003, 119 et seq. (133).

⁴¹ R. Bernhardt, "Article 103", in B. Simma (ed.), *The Charter of the United Nations. A Commentary*, 2002,

⁴² A. Orakhelashvili, "Security Council Acts: Meaning and Standards of Review", *Max Planck UNYB* 11 (2007), 143 et seq. (150)

⁴³ Application of the Convention on the Prevention and Punishment of the Crime of Genocide (Bosnia and Herzegovina v. Serbia and Montenegro), Separate Opinion of Judge ad hoc Lauterpacht, ICJ Reports 1993, 407 et seq. (440 para. 100).

⁴⁴ C. Olivier, "Human Rights Law and the International Fight against Terrorism: How do Security Council Resolutions Impact on States' Obligations under International Human Rights Law? (Revisiting Security Council Resolution 1373)", *Nord. J. Int'l L.* 73 (2004), 399 et seq. (414).

United Nations. Promoting and encouraging respect for human rights and fundamental freedoms are among these purposes, and therefore the Security Council must always take them into account when acting under Chapter VII.

III. THE UNITED NATIONS COLLECTIVE SECURITY SYSTEM VIS-À-VIS COLLECTIVE DEFENCE

The concept of Collective Security System has been gaining a new credibility in contemporary international relations. Preservation of international peace and security as well as securing of development through cooperation at all levels of international relations can be described as the two major objectives of our generation. Collective Security of peace and collective efforts for development stand accepted as the two means for attaining these objectives. The notion of Collective Security forwarded by scholars are deemed to apply global security interests in a broad manner, to avoid grouping powers into opposing camps, and refusing to draw dividing lines that would leave anyone out.

Since 1945, the Collective Security system has been tried in a number of cases. It was used for the first time for meeting the Korean Crisis of 1950. However, during the period 1956-90 the Collective Security system under the United Nations failed to work successfully in securing international peace and security because of several factors. The cold war between the two super powers, the bipolarity in international relations, the inability of the General Assembly to act under the Uniting for Peace Resolution, and the changed nature of aggression and war, all combined to prevent the operationalization of the Collective Security system during this period. The Lebanon crisis, the Iran-Iraq War and several other local wars kept on going and the UN failed to act. During the Cold War various treaties were formalized as a part of bloc formations in case the UN too failed. Under these arrangements participant states committed support in defence of a member state if it was attacked by another state outside the organization. Such treaties formed the base of a newer concept, which seemed similar to Collective Security but was termed as Collective Self-Defence. On a comparative analysis Collective Security is differentiated from Collective Self-Defence by the pledge that the defence would be against a threat from an external country. The most relevant example of Collective Self-Defence is Article V of the

NATO treaty⁴⁵. This article was invoked after the 9-11 attacks in the US for other NATO members to provide assistance to the US war on Terror in Afghanistan. The only advantage that may be seen in favour of Collective Self-Defence in the modern day is the fact that it also takes the presence of non-state actors into account. Thus, the countries can take action against terrorists even in the backdrop of failing UN action.

However, during the last decade of the 20th century, the Collective Security System began acting as a popular and useful device for the preservation of international peace and security. It was successfully operationalized to meet the Iraqi aggression and occupation of Kuwait. To meet the violations of international peace and security resulting from the Iraqi act of aggression, the Security Council first called upon Iraq to vacate aggression, and when it failed to comply with, enforced economic sanctions against Iraq. The Security Council later on decided to take military action, i.e. Collective Security action against Iraq. A UN peacekeeping force was raised under the US leadership and to which 42 countries contributed their armed contingents. On 17th January 1991, a Collective Security war against Iraq was initiated and within few days Iraq's resistance was neutralized and liberation of Kuwait was secured. Collective Security war was successfully made to secure international peace and security and to negate Iraq's aggression.

The collective security action against Iraq was successful primarily due to the keen interest taken by the US and the inability or unwillingness on the part of the other four permanent members of Security Council to oppose the former. The internal troubles of the (erstwhile) USSR compelled it to support the US sponsored decisions and policies. The decision to continue sanctions against, Iraq even after the end of its aggression against Kuwait reflected the problems involved in keeping a collective security war limited and confined.

After the collapse of the Soviet Union, Russia became its successor state. Its economic dependence upon the US and some other Western countries began compelling it to accommodate the US view point in the UN and other international fora. China also began feeling isolated after the collapse of socialist regimes in the USSR and other socialist-states of Europe and thus, also accommodated US

⁴⁵ North Atlantic Treaty, Apr. 4, 1949, 63 Stat. 2241, 34 U.N.T.S. 243.

positions. The changed international scenario of the post-cold war, the post-USSR and the Post-Warsaw bloc international system, made decision-making by the US led Security Council easier. New development gave a new strength of the operationalization of Collective Security. In one form or another, the UN Collective Security operations for preserving peace and security began operating in more than 20 different places for example, the 2001 war against Afghanistan's Al Qaeda's terrorist regime was made under the Charter. However in 2003 the USA decided to go to a war against Iraq in the name of eliminating weapons of mass destruction (WMD). Although such a US action came as a source of erosion of collective security, in international relations as the UN has not given its sanctions to such a war, it cannot be said to be the demise of Collective Security.

In spite of the enormous strides made by collective security in ensuring world peace and security, many see Collective Self-Defence as an alternative to Collective Security. This is because in the modern day with terrorism rising as a challenge in the face of Collective Security principles, the persistent inability of the UN to provide and maintain a functioning system can reasonably be viewed as a massive, radical multilateral failure of consideration. To add to the wounds of the UN if some members choose to suspend or even terminate their performance of the restrictions encapsulated in Article 51, the UN would be reduced to a mere vegetable like presence.

Though contrasting concepts, Collective Security and Collective Self Defence are synonymous in a lot of ways. Collective Self-Defence finds its foundation in multilateral alliances such as NATO, the presence of which entails benefits as well as risks. Collective Self-Defence allows countries in smaller groups to, at their own initiative perform complementary functions of the UN. On one side, collective pooling of resources reduces a single state's cost of providing fully for its security. Smaller groups such as NATO ensure that funding collectively allows them to build infrastructure, education or health, since they can count on other members to come to their defence, if needed. In addition to this, since they have already taken aggressive action they also can have peacekeeping missions at lower costs in those countries something that the UN finds difficult when it enters to rebuild conflict hit areas.

However, it may be too premature to call Collective Defence as an alternative to the concept of Collective Security as it also involves risky commitments. Member states can become embroiled in costly wars in which neither the direct victim nor the aggressor benefits. The policy of non-interference of the UN and its sticking to just peacekeeping missions for security on the other hand has ensured a better result with budgets almost a 10th of what the NATO spent in Iraq alone⁴⁶.

IV. A CRITICAL ANALYSIS OF THE UNITED NATIONS COLLECTIVE SECURITY SYSTEM.

As a device of crisis management through power-management and as a means of securing international peace and security, Collective Security has been the object of severe criticism. The concept of Collective Security, as laid down in the Charter, has two inherent limitations. Firstly, it accepts the right of the states to undertake war as a measure of self-defence against any aggression which, in practice gives a legal basis to an aggression or war in the name of action in self-defence. Secondly, it admits the right of the nations to establish regional defence pacts and organisations for protecting their security. Thus, it admits regional security systems as devices for preserving peace and security. The working of regional security systems has in-fact been a source of strain upon international peace and security.

In addition, the member states have accepted certain limitations on self-defence, which are the reciprocal of its promise of collective security. Collective Security as a concept contrasts with retaliatory strategies of engaging in war for immediate national interest. However, in both the cases of the League and the UN the most important thing that has lacked is the fact that member states have not co-operated with each other. It was this lack of co-operation that replaced the League in the first place.

One of the basic principles of Collective Security is that all the states should have an equal say in arriving at collective security decisions. In actual operation, it fails to work on the principle of equality. Powerful states always dominate collective security decisions and actions. In fact, only the powerful states can play an effective role in

⁴⁶ Anthony Cordesman, '*US Military Spending: The Cost of War*'. Available at the Centre for strategic and International Studies website: <https://www.csis.org/analysis/us-military-spending-cost-wars>

executing a collective security action. Most times powerful states are reluctant to put their power behind a collective security action, which does not strictly conform to their national interests.

Another major limitation of the Collective Security system is the absence of a permanent peace keeping force. It is only after a decision of the Security Council to take military action against an aggressor is taken that the constitution of a collective security military force is initiated. This process is so slow and difficult that it takes a long time to raise the force and press it into service. The time-gap between the date of aggression and the date on which the United Nations is actually able to send its peace keeping force for restoring peace is very big, and the aggressor gets all the time needed for reaping the fruits of aggression.

During the last two decades, UN economic sanctions have come under harsh criticism. The experience of the sanctions imposed on Iraq by the UN Security Council in the 1990s, and still in place, shows the ethical and legal concerns of sanctions. The humanitarian problems caused by economic sanctions against Iraq illustrate their adverse impact on the population⁴⁷. For a long time, different UN organs and humanitarian agencies have called for an end to many of the sanctions in order to facilitate a greater flow of food and medicines⁴⁸. The UN General Assembly's debate emphasised the need to lift the sanctions in order to end human suffering in Iraq⁴⁹, although the international community must ensure compliance

⁴⁷ S. Willett, *The Gulf Crisis: Economic Implications*, 1990; P. Clawson, *How Has Saddam Survived?, Economic Sanctions: 1990-93*, 1993. UNICEF Press Release Doc. CF/DOC/PR/1999/29 of 12 August 1999. In 1999, after conducting the first surveys since 1991 of child and maternal mortality in Iraq, UNICEF concluded that in the heavily-populated southern and central parts of the country, children under five are dying at more than twice the rate they were 10 years ago. Richard Garfield, an expert on the effects of sanctions on civilians, states that "the underlying causes of these excess deaths include contaminated water, lack of high quality foods, inadequate breastfeeding, poor weaning practices, and inadequate supplies in the curative health-care system", R. Garfield, "Morbidity and mortality among Iraqi children from 1990 through 1998: assessing the impact of the Gulf war and economic sanctions", unprinted version, July 1999, available on Campaign Against Sanctions on Iraq <www.casi.org.uk/info/garfield/dr-garfield.html>. In his opinion, the lack of food due to sanctions translated into a 32 per cent drop in per capita calorie intake compared to before the Gulf war. According to the Government of Iraq, by 1997, only half of the water treatment capacity of the country was operational.

⁴⁸ D. Jehl, "UN Official Calls for an End of Sanctions against Iraq", *International Herald Tribune*, 21 September 1999, 10.

⁴⁹ UN Press Release GA/9618 of 30 September 1999.

with the sanctions imposed by the Security Council as measures to restore international peace and security. Many lessons have been learned from the economic sanctions against Iraq and the implementation of the oil for food program⁵⁰ as the sanctions have affected the civilian population more than the Iraqi Government. Indeed, the Government of Iraq pointed to sanctions as the primary cause of suffering in Iraq, while others blamed the authorities in Baghdad. A reliable assessment right at the beginning could have identified the processes that affected humanitarian conditions, and could therefore have assisted in mitigating the unintended negative consequences of the sanctions. In most of these cases sanctions have unintentionally contributed to the emergence of black markets, creating huge profit-making opportunities for ruling elites and their collaborators⁵¹. Worst of all, economic sanctions tend to hit the wrong targets; instead of the regime, the population at large and particularly the weakest in society become the true victims. Faced with these situations, scholars have condemned economic sanctions as being inhumane and destructive diplomatic measures that jeopardise human rights in target countries⁵².

The international community's efforts to combat international terrorism are an excellent illustration of the difficulties faced by the UN collective security system. The effort to maintain international peace and security on the one hand, and the principle of proportionality and the need to protect human rights on the other. The Security Council, being the legitimate authority in matters of collective security, by adopting the necessary measures to prevent acts of terror or any breach of the peace is duty-bound to minimise "collateral damage" by considering the specific means to be

⁵⁰ E. de Wet, "Human rights limitations to economic enforcement measures under article 41 of the United Nations Charter and the Iraq sanctions regime", *LJIL* 14 (2001), 277 et seq. (282); E. Hoskins, "The Humanitarian Impacts of Economic Sanctions and War in Iraq", in: Th. Weiss (ed.), *Political Gain and Civilian Pain*, 1997, 92 et seq. (106-108).

⁵¹ 2005 World Summit Outcome, A/RES/60/1 of 16 September 2005, para 50.

⁵² L. Damrosch, "The Civilian Impact of Economic Sanctions", in: L. Damrosch (ed.), *Enforcing Restraint: Collective Intervention in Internal Conflicts*, 1993, 279. G. Simons, *The Scourging of Iraq*, 1998, 33-34; D. Malone, "The UN Security Council: 10 lessons from Iraq on regulations and accountability", *Journal of International Law and International Relations* 2 (2006), 1 et seq.; A. Baram, "The Effects of Iraqi Sanctions: Statistical Pitfalls and Responsibility", *The Middle East Journal* 54 (2000), 194 et seq.; E. Hoskins, "The Humanitarian Impacts of Economic Sanctions and War in Iraq", in: T.G. Weiss (ed.), *Political gain and civilian pain*, 1997, 91 et seq.; E. Hoskins, *The Impact of Sanctions: A Study of UNICEF's Perspective*, 1998; L. Minear/ D. Cortright/ J. Wagler/ G. Lopez/ T. Weiss, *Towards More Humane and Effective Sanctions Management: Enhancing the Capacity of the United Nations System*, Occasional Paper No. 3, 1998.

applied in each case. The fact that the Charter recognizes the inherent right of individual and collective self-defence is now being used by member nations to circumvent the binding obligations. This has garnered legitimacy in the light of the UN's inability in the modern day to apply Collective Security against non-state actors who sponsor terrorism.

As noted by the High-level Panel on Threats, Challenges and Change, if the Security Council is to win the respect it must have as the primary body in the collective security system, it is critical that its most important and influential decisions, those with large-scale life-and-death impact, be better made, better substantiated and better communicated. In particular, in deciding whether or not to authorize the use of force, the Council should adopt and systematically address a set of agreed guidelines, deciding not whether force can legally be used but whether, as a matter of good conscience and good sense, it should be⁵³.

The Report of the Secretary-General "In Larger Freedom: Towards Security, Development, and Human Rights For All", outlines that "the task is not to find alternatives to the Security Council as a source of authority but to make it work better⁵⁴ within the competences of Chapter VII. The language of Chapter VII is inherently broad enough, and has been interpreted broadly enough, to allow the Security Council to approve any chosen coercive action, including military action, against a state when it deems this "necessary to maintain or restore international peace and security⁵⁵.

Some critics hold the view the Collective Security system is a dangerous system as it can transform a local war into a global war involving all the nations for example, the situation in Syria which is gradually metamorphosing as a war between on one side, the Syrian government and its foreign allies, and on the other side, the rebels and their foreign allies.

⁵³ Doc. A/59/565 of 2 December 2004, para. 204.

⁵⁴ Doc. A/59/2005 of 21 March 2005, para. 126.

⁵⁵ Article 42 UN Charter.

A further drawback of the UN Collective Security System is that whereas elaborate provisions have been laid down for implementing the system, no provision has been made regarding the method of terminating the Collective Security action. Thus, the collective security system is an idealistic and limited system.

However, despite these points of criticism and recognized weaknesses of the Collective Security system, it cannot be denied that the system has not been totally meaningless and without positive features. It has brought into vision the idea and possibility of collective steps for the preservation of world peace through crisis management in the event of a war. The chances for a more purposeful and successful use of Collective Security in this post-cold war world have brightened; as it is currently it is being operationalized in several different parts of the world.

V. CONCLUSION

Despite the mandate in the UN Charter and prior to it, the League of Nations, the very legal framework to ensure Collective Security, in its aims as an integrated whole has failed because smaller group of countries with singular political aims, such as NATO, performing similar functions has undermined global consensus and overall security. This has resulted in Kelsen's view of Collective Security as a legal aspect of a political balance of power, to be segregated at the hands of the few superpowers. In conclusion, with no other alternative, it seems that theoretically, self-defence may be the new security.